

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Smart Temperature-Sensitive Injectable Methylcellulose-Based Hydrogels: Design and Optimization for Sustained Drug Release

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Figure S1. Molecular structures of the polymers tested in the study: Methylcellulose (MC) (a), Polyethylene glycol (PEG) (b), Chitosan (CH) (c) and Pectin (Pec) (d).

Figure S2. Temperature ramps of gel-sol transition of four different hydrogels. Initially the hydrogels were gelation at 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Samples were cooled from 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ at 1 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$. Frequency was 1 Hz and shear strain 3%. T gel-sol transition is defined as the crossover of storage G' and loss modulus G'' . MC (a), MC/PEG (b), MC/CH (c) and MC/Pec (d).

Figure S3. Rheological analysis. Average gelation temperature (a) and average gelation time at 37 °C (b) for MC, MC/PEG and MC/Pec hydrogels. Each point represents the mean \pm SD (n = 3).

Figure S4. SEM investigation: morphological analysis of hydrogel formulations MC (a, b), MC/PEG (c, d), MC/CH (e, f) and MC/Pec (g, h). Magnification 60X, scale bar 200 μm (left) and magnification 200X, scale bar 100 μm (right).

Video S1-S4. Injectability of four different hydrogels. The videos show the injectability of MC (S1), MC/PEG (S2), MC/CH (S3) and MC/Pec (S4) at room temperature, through a G22 needle. For making the visualization easier, the hydrogels are loaded with rhodamine B conferring the typical pink colour.